

Perceived Influence of Information and Communication Technology Skills on Business Education Students Entrepreneurial Intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria

BY

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Abstract

The study assessed the perceived influence of ICT skills on business education students' entrepreneurial intention in polytechnics in North-East Nigeria. Business education prepares students for paid jobs and for self-employments through equipping them with knowledge of ICT facilities to enable them have entrepreneurial intention to reduce unemployment. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study was anchored on the theory of planned behaviour. The study adopted explanatory mixed method research design. The population was 1003 respondents, comprising 103 lecturers, 874 students and 26 class representatives in polytechnics in North-East Nigeria. The random sampling techniques was used to select 37 lecturers, 207 students and 9 class representatives, the sample of the study was therefore, 253. A 54-item questionnaire with 4-point rating scale was the instrument used for quantitative data collection. A structured interview was used to collect qualitative data. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. Cronbach Alpha procedure was used to test the reliability of the instrument and the result yielded a reliability coefficient index of 0.88. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed among others that access to ICT facilities influenced business education students entrepreneurial intention with weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.22 and 0.60; Microsoft Word skills influenced business education students entrepreneurial intention to a high extent with a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.37 and 0.56. The findings on all the two hypotheses tested revealed that there were significant differences in the mean ratings of federal and state institutions regarding access to ICT facilities and Microsoft Word skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention ($t_{238} = 10.812, P < 0.05, 8.75$). Based on the findings of the study it was recommended among others that TETFUND and managements of polytechnics should ensure that ICT facilities are always available for effective and efficient teaching of business education students so that they will be motivated to have entrepreneurial intention.

Keywords: *ICT, Skills, Business Education, Entrepreneurial intention*

Introduction

Education can be likened to an engine house that shapes the affairs, talents and economy of a nation. Education is said to be the key to success which means it is the key that triggers off the engine and propeller that spurs development in motion. Entrepreneurial education therefore, is the key to both self and national development. Any individual, society or nation that aspires for true independence must have the goal of attainment of self-sufficiency which can be found in entrepreneurship education. A nation that cannot produce most of her goods but depends mostly on other nations for survival cannot worth its independence. In like manner any graduate that cannot aspire for self-dependence through self-employment is liable to suffer especially in this unemployment era. This is the reason why one of the national education objectives contained in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) is the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities, capabilities and competencies, both natural and physical, as equipment for the development of self, society and nation. The implication of this is that graduates from a school at any stage should be able to fit into the world of work as employers or self-employed individuals. Incidentally, this cannot be achieved without sound entrepreneurial education.

Skills are the abilities acquired through training to do a particular job or activity. Skill is the ability to perform a thing with determined results within a given period of time, energy, or both. It can often be divided into domain-general and domain-specific skills. A skill is an activity, which is developed by a person with time and becomes automatic in terms of performing it (Nnaji 2019). The author stresses that certain skill can be considered acquired when a person can perform it without thinking about the technique of performing this action or dividing a process into conventional parts. It is an ability learned to act with determined results with good performance often within a given timeframe, energy, or both. A skill generally requires certain environmental stimuli and situations to assess the level of proficiency demonstrated and used (Mamman & Saba, 2021). Skill therefore, involves a practical knowledge, coupled with clearness, expertise, dexterity and ability to carry out a duty which must have been acquired or learnt in a formal or informal setting through learning, practice and experience.

Nnaji and Pyiki (2019) observe that business education is education for and about training in business skills, competencies that are required in business offices, for clerical, secretarial and teaching jobs and that which enables the individual to identify his/her potentials. The author maintained that Business Education prepares and equips business graduates for employment, participation and recognition in the business world. Due to the increasingly complex nature of organizations and businesses in the developing world, there is the need that the business education imparts relevant skills to enable the graduates meet up with global competitiveness. Etonyeaku (2013) views business education as a formidable force that will equip individuals with appropriate skills, knowledge, abilities and competencies that will enable them to be self-employed and self-reliant which will lead to sustainable economic development. The bottom line is that business education is a special education which focuses on training the recipient to be relevant in the world of work either by being an entrepreneur or by working for another.

The willingness of an individual to show entrepreneurial behavior and engage in entrepreneurial activities related with self-employment initiative and new business start-ups is characterized as entrepreneurial intention. Individuals would select professions in entrepreneurship depending on their judgments of its fit and desirability (Dohse, Walter, & Asuamah 2013).

Polytechnic students consist of male and female students who spend two years in the National Diploma (ND) courses and two years in Higher National Diploma (HND) courses. Some of these students have entrepreneurial intention and the question is who is an entrepreneur?

Entrepreneur is the coordinator of all other factors of production. He is the owner of a business who controls all aspects of his business. An entrepreneur seizes all available opportunities to make profit. Olaniyi (2016) asserts that entrepreneurship conjures up visions of active, purposeful men and women accomplishing significant achievements. An entrepreneur needs Microsoft word skills desperately because the knowledge of Microsoft word skills determine the success of a business. Therefore, based on the foregoing, a problem is envisaged if business education students are not equipped with unfettered Microsoft word knowledge and skills that would boost their entrepreneurial intentions and quest to own businesses.

Polytechnics in Northeastern states of Nigeria are both State and Federal Polytechnics situated in this area. Northeast Nigeria is one of the six geo-political zones in the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The North eastern zone comprises of six states namely; Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe States.

Statement of the Problem

Nigerian government made some efforts to reduce unemployment rate through the introduction of information and communication technology and entrepreneurship as courses into the Business Education and other programmes of study in Nigerian tertiary education. The purpose of introducing these courses is that students can be equipped with skills for self-employment after graduation. Yet, the rate of unemployment keeps increasing at alarming rate on a daily basis. These graduates are seeing ideal without corresponding career possibilities and without recourse to use the knowledge of ICT skills and facilities for entrepreneurial intention. It is important to note that the graduates of business education are expected to develop different entrepreneurial skills and abilities that will enable them start up small scale businesses if they are unable to find white collar jobs. It has not been so and their jobless condition has been linked to several forms of criminality. Business Education graduates who have gone through the undergraduates programme in higher institutions are expected to have acquired ICT skills such as keyboarding skill, word processing skill, database management system skill, webpage design skill, desktop publishing skill and competencies that will enable them to own businesses and become employers of labour but this has not been so. The absence of these makes graduates to roam about the streets looking for white-collar jobs that are rarely available. Most times these graduates resort to violent lives such as criminality, kidnapping, banditry, cultism and others because of lack of job. It is against this situation that it becomes necessary for the researchers to conduct this study in order to determine the Perceived Influence of ICT facilities and skills on Business Education students Entrepreneurial Intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the Perceived Influence of Skills on Business Education Students Entrepreneurial Intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to determine the extent to which:

1. Database management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.
2. Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study.

1. To what extent does Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated, were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers, instructors and students on the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Theoretical Frame work

21st Century Skills Learning Theory by Mcleod, Bathon and Richardson (2011).

The 21st Century skills learning theory lays emphasis on holistic learning and insists that learning should be integrated, holistic, connected, skillful, relevant, adaptable, student centered, project based, authentic and convenient. The learning theory states that providing students with education that is relevant to the society in which they live is preponderant. There is the need for students to be skillful and adaptable; they also, need to be able to work independently with ICT and communicate effectively. They also, need to be sovereign while possessing the ability to work on team projects. 21st Century skills learning theory emphasizes on the need to consider a professional and societal environment in which access to knowledge is immediate, and in which one-to-many styles of communication are rampant. The 21st century learning equips individuals with necessary skills to become active members of the society. 21st Century learning and constructivism are student centered learning and they are geared towards student in-depth understanding of content in order to work creatively with it. It is suggested that learning that is holistic, meaningful, and engages students academically, emotionally, morally and physically will best enable the development of these skills in the student. Appropriate business education students training will facilitate multiple ICT skills by stimulating and developing all of them in the learner (Gardner, 1983, Edelson, 2001, Singha, Ong, Mohtar, Singh, & Mostafae 2020).

Skills

Skill is the ability to acquire practical knowledge in new conditions and on the basis of the abilities and experiences a person had previously. A skill is an activity, which is developed by a person with time and becomes automatic in terms of performing it. A certain skill can be considered acquired when a person can perform it without thinking about the technique of performing this action or dividing a process into conventional parts. It is an ability learned to act with determined results with good performance often within a given timeframe, energy, or both. A skill generally requires certain environmental stimuli and situations to assess the level of proficiency demonstrated and used (Mamman & Saba, 2021). Similarly, Ovbiagele and Mgbonyebi (2018) describe skill as ability to do a thing perfectly well, and this gained through education and experience. The duo maintained that skill is a person's competencies in performing specific task, gained through training or experience. It means that skill involves a practical knowledge, in addition to clearness, expertise, dexterity and ability to perform a duty. Skill can be acquired or learnt in a formal or informal setting through practice and experience. According to Ekwue et al. (2019), skills have become increasingly important in the globalised world. The shifting of demand for skills has necessitated the availability of highly skilled labour. In this technological advanced challenging environment, the role of higher education institutions is not only to produce graduates with specific areas of specialization, but more importantly, to develop graduate skills that match the demands of industry. As such tertiary institutions are under intense pressure from stakeholders, especially industry, to equip graduates with more than just academic skills (Saad & Majid, 2014). Skill is the ability to perform perfectly well with dexterity and fact through what has been learnt and practiced in

training. It is usually associated with particular occupational area (Ezeabii, Nwokike & Jim, 2017).

ICT skill is the ability to use ICT facilities effectively to perform various duties. ICT skills are abilities that help you understand and operate a wide range of technology software. This can include helping users with tasks on computers, such as making video calls, searching on the internet or using a mobile device like a tablet or phone. ICT skills are abilities that help you understand and operate a wide range of technology software. ICT skills can also include any direct interaction with technology, including turning on a computer, using hardware to print and copy documents and using digital cameras to capture photographs or video footage. The following are some ICT skills that are required for entrepreneurial intention according to Indeed Editorial Team (2023):

Technological Knowledge

Working in ICT requires an understanding of company preferences of technology for daily duties. This can include general experience with computers and mobile devices, like phones and tablets. This knowledge can also include basic operations, such as maintaining and updating technology for increased efficiency.

Online Research

Online research is the method of collecting information using the internet. This involves using search engines and educational sites for research and setting up methods of accumulating data. These methods may include customer surveys, online interviews and metric data gathering.

Social Media Management

Social media management is the process of gathering information from social media audiences and developing strategies tailored to their preferences. You can accomplish this through creating and distributing content for social media profiles, monitoring online conversations and measuring engagement with profiles for a company. Compiling social media data can provide fundamental information that can help organizations make well-informed decisions on marketing strategies.

Netiquette

Netiquette is a set of guidelines that ensures respect for online communication. These rules apply to multiple aspects of the internet, including email, messaging forums and video and audio chats. Netiquette involves learning how to conduct yourself in an online community and extending the teaching of those guidelines to co-workers who may not have as much experience with internet communication methods.

Data Management

Data management is the process of collecting, organizing and storing massive quantities of business metrics for analysis and future decisions. This can include managing database and spreadsheet software for businesses and organizing the data for others to understand. It can also include creating folders and files on an organization's network and knowing how to upload, download, copy or move these files between the company's computers. In addition, data management involves managing online accounts and keeping track of the usernames and passwords for these accounts.

Desktop Publishing

Desktop publishing is the creation of documents using software that prepares the digital information for transition to a physical medium, whether it's a webpage, postcard, brochure, business card or label. It can allow companies to use marketing information to create visual displays that attract customers. Having desktop publishing skills may allow you to work as a graphic designer and create the original assets, or you may work alongside a graphic designer to prepare the created assets for printing.

Word Processing

Word processing is the production or manipulation of text on a computer using specialized software. You can prepare a document for different uses by typing written communications and formatting the document according to an organization's desired specifications. Another part of word processing is conducting data entry, which can involve organizing data in spreadsheets, and presenting this data through visual aids that you can create using slideshow creation programs.

Collaboration

Collaboration is the concept of working with one or more people to complete a task or project. Technology professionals can use their collaboration skills to help other coworkers with their technological challenges, such as helping them learn new software or troubleshoot issues. Connecting your coworkers through online communication services can also encourage collaboration through the internet.

Problem-solving

Problem-solving skills can help you determine the source of an issue and work toward finding an effective solution. It often involves analysis, active listening, research and decision-making. Those with problem-solving skills may specialize in researching or analyzing and organizing data, or they may use their skills to help organizations find the technology or programs that can best meet their needs.

Organization

Organizational skills include the management of your time, workspace and energy to encourage the completion of all your current tasks. Organizational skills can also include managing schedules digitally, organizing files for easier access and cleaning out technology for better efficiency. This skill may be helpful in positions where you are constantly maintaining computer systems.

Business Education

According to Okeke (2023), Business education is a branch of education that involves teaching the skills and operations of the business industry. This field of education occurs at multiple levels, including secondary and higher education. Consequently, the mission of business education at the college and the university level is to train the necessary manpower for industry, business, public and private business establishments, including manpower for teaching. Thus, business education opens various career opportunities to its graduates namely, teaching in schools at various levels depending on the level of degree obtained, working in commerce and the public sector of the economy, undergoing advanced studies in business, taking up management positions in various organizations and developing training programmes for industries and businesses. Business education is a major component of vocational education. Business education is also design field of study for the development of skills, attitudes, appreciation, creativity as well as creation of awareness and competencies in the office work and business world. It is a programme of study that equips students with relevant skills for self and societal development. Simply put together business education is the type of education that prepares the youth for occupational positions in various offices, be it government or private. It is education that prepares students for the world of work and the world of business.

Nnaji (2014) concurred that business education is education for and about training in business skills, competencies required for use in business offices, clerical occupations and that which gives occupational identity. The author maintained that business education is an academic programme offered at the tertiary level of education in Nigeria that is directed towards empowering learners with business skills. Njoku (2015) explained that business education is a programme of instruction, which consists of office education, which is a vocational education programme for office career workers through initial refresher and upgrading education. He further explained that general business education is a programme that

provides learners with information and competencies which are needed by all in managing personal business affairs and in using the services of business. Ayelotan and Sholagbade (2014) opined that business education is a programme of instruction which consists of two parts: the Office Education (presently known as Office Technology and Management) for effective careers and the general business education program that provides students with information and competencies. It is a type of education which provides skills, knowledge and attitude necessary for effective employment in specific occupation. (Shaibu, Ameh and Barinem, 2014) stated that it is the deliberate intent of teachers to inform students about economics and business concepts and skills that might be of use in later life. It is meant to equip the youths with certain economic and business concepts as a vehicle for better understanding and analysis of the dynamic business work.

Methods

The mixed method research design was adopted for the study. The Explanatory Confirmation design was employed for the study. The descriptive research design was employed for the quantitative aspect of the study since it sought to document and describe what exists or the present status of existence or absence of what was investigated (Nworgu, 2015). The population of the study for the quantitative data comprises 103 OTM lecturers and 874 students in Polytechnics in the North-East. For the qualitative data, OTM class representatives in these polytechnics were used and they are 26 in number making the total population of the study 1,003 OTM lecturers and students respectively. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 37 lecturers out of the 103 population of lecturers and 207 students out of 874 population of students for the quantitative study while 9 class representative out of 26 population of class representatives were selected for the qualitative study. The total sample of the study was therefore, 253. The research instruments was structured questionnaire and semi-structured interview which was developed by the researchers after proper review of literature. The 54-item questionnaire was titled “ Perceived Influence of ICT Skills on Students Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire (PICTSSEIQ).” The Questionnaire was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent, High Extent, Moderate Extent and Low Extent with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The second instrument was the interview schedule which was used to collect the qualitative data. Interviews goes a long way in helping research subjects to open up and air their views in a very magnificent way based on their experiences on what is being investigated (Egbri, 2015).

The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Office Technology and Management the Polytechnic, Bali, one from Department of Measurement and Evaluation Taraba State University. The researchers conducted a pilot study at Kaduna Polytechnic. Twenty (20) Copies of the questionnaire were administered to lecturers and students in the department of Office Technology and Management. The data generated from the pilot study was analysed using Cronbach Alpha reliability method to determine the internal consistency of the instrument and it yielded a reliability co-efficient index of 0.88. The quantitative data was collected by the researchers with the help of one research assistant from each of the polytechnics under study. The researchers briefly explained to the research assistants how to administer and retrieve the questionnaires. The questionnaire and the interview schedule were administered simultaneously. The 37 copies of the questionnaire for lecturers were all collected and properly filled and used for the study. While out of the 207 copies of questionnaire administered to students 203 were returned and properly filled and used for the study which represents (98.06%) return rate.

Mean and Standard Deviation were employed to analyse the data which were collected to answer the research questions. The null hypothesis one was tested using t-test while null hypothesis 2 was tested using ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance at the relevant degree of

freedom. Decision rule with respect to research questions was based on the principle of upper and lower limits of the mean. Thus:

SECTIONS B1-B4:

Very High Extent	4	3.50 – 4.00
High Extent	3	2.50 – 3.49
Low Extent	2	1.50 – 2.49
Very Low Extent	1	1.00 – 1.49

Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the degree of responses; any item with standard deviation of less than 1.96 indicated that there was not much variability from the mean or from the responses of the respondents. On the other hand, any standard deviation above 1.96 indicated that there are wide variations in the responses of the respondents. The data collected from the interview was analysed using content analysis. Any null hypothesis whose p-value is equal or greater than the Alpha value ($0.05 \geq$) and at the derived degree of freedom was retained and concluded that there was no significant difference between the respondents otherwise it was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does Database Management skills acquisition influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Ability to start Microsoft Access	3.42	0.50	High Extent
2.	Ability to create a database	3.31	0.46	High Extent
3.	Ability to add fields, tables or application parts	3.60	0.50	Very High Extent
4.	Ability to create queries, forms, reports and macros	3.35	0.48	High Extent
5.	Ability to create database using a template	3.52	0.62	Very High Extent
6.	Ability to click on file tab, close and display a new tab	3.14	0.59	High Extent
7.	Ability to query the tables and forms created	3.34	0.47	High Extent
8.	Copy data from another source into an Access table	3.29	0.57	High Extent
9.	Import, append, or link to data from another source	3.24	0.46	High Extent
10.	Ability to add an application part	3.22	0.54	High Extent
11.	Ability to open an Access existing database	3.44	0.52	High Extent
12.	Ability to type a file name in the box	3.18	0.67	High Extent
13.	Ability to browse for location to put a database	3.36	0.42	High Extent
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		3.33	0.52	High Extent

Source: *Field Survey, 2023*

Table 1 revealed the responses of the respondents regarding the extent to which Database Management skills acquisition influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria with mean scores of (3.42, 3.31, 3.60, 3.35, 3.52, 3.14, 3.34, 3.29, 3.24, 3.22, 3.44, 3.18 and 3.36 respectively). All the 13 item constructs have standard deviation ranging from 0.42 to 0.67 which means that the responses of the respondents are not widely spread as they are close to their respective mean scores. Table 1

therefore, reveals that the respondents agreed to high extent in all the constructs. The table shows a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.33 and 0.52 respectively. This implies that Database Management skills acquisition influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East.

Research Question 2: To what extent does Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Ability to insert a new worksheets at will	3.73	0.44	Very High Extent
2.	Ability to use the time saving shortcut keys	3.77	0.43	Very High Extent
3.	Ability to get quick sum of numbers	3.57	0.50	Very High Extent
4.	Ability to filter data	3.55	0.50	Very High Extent
5.	Ability to paste special feature	3.32	0.47	High Extent
6.	Ability to insert random numbers	3.47	0.50	High Extent
7.	Ability to create goal seeking analysis tool	3.37	0.48	High Extent
8.	Ability to insert random fraction numbers	3.36	0.48	High Extent
9.	Ability to insert serial numbers	3.22	0.54	High Extent
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		3.48	0.48	High Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Analysis in Table 2 reveals the mean responses of respondents regarding the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria with mean scores of (3.73, 3.77, 3.57, 3.55, 3.32, 3.47, 3.37, 3.36 and 3.22 respectively). All 9 items have a standard deviation range from 0.43 and 0.54 which are below the fixed value of 1.96, which means that the responses of the respondents are not too widespread as it is close to the mean. The Table reveals that Microsoft Excel skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. This is supported by an average mean and standard deviation of (mean = 3.48, SD = 0.48) respectively.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of the difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	37	3.71	0.00				
				11.76	238	0.000	Ho3 Rejected
Students	203	3.23	0.39				

Source: Field survey, 2023

P < 0.05

The data in Table 3 reveals that 37 respondents are lecturers while, 203 respondents are students. The respondents that are lecturers have higher mean score but lower standard deviations ($\bar{x} = 3.71$; $SD = 0.00$) than respondents that are students ($\bar{x} = 3.23$; $SD = 0.39$). Their responses are close to the mean as the standard deviations are very low. The table revealed that there was significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria ($t_{238} = 11.76$, $P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria was rejected. This implies that lecturers and students of business education differ in their responses regarding the extent to which Database Management skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers, instructors and students on the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA result showing difference in the mean ratings of lecturers, instructors and students on the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Senatorial Districts	Number	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	F	Sig.	Decision
Lecturers	28	3.90	0.13			
Instructors	9	3.11	0.31	172.015	0.000	Rejected
Students	203	2.33	0.42			

Source: Field survey, 2023

$P < 0.05$

The descriptive statistics (frequency, mean and standard deviation) as presented in Table 4 shows lecturers, instructors and students have mean scores of 3.90, 3.11, and 2.33 and corresponding standard deviation of 0.13, 0.31, 0.42 respectively. The result of analysis of variance as presented in Table 4 reveals that the calculated value of F is 172.015 ($F_{2,238} = 172.015$) and the observed probability value is 0.000 which is less than the fixed probability value of 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that the null hypotheses which states that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers, instructors and students on the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria is rejected. This implies that lecturers, instructors and students differ in their responses regarding the extent to which Microsoft Excel skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention.

Analysis of the Qualitative Data

The qualitative data are analysed using content analysis and the identified themes are related to the purpose of the study since the interview was semi-structured. The themes are Database Management skills, Microsoft Excel skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intentions in polytechnics in North-east.

Database Management Skills

The class representatives said that database management is very necessary to business education students entrepreneurial intention. They said it will assist them to create access to store the business lists of data in tables, which allow business owners to store even more

detailed information. It will enable one to store information according to order made by the customer and date the delivery will be made.

All the class representatives said Database allow their users to enter, access, and analyse their data quickly and easily. They are such a useful tool that you see them all the time. It helps an entrepreneur or the employee work as a store employee to use a computer to see whether an item was in stock or not. All the respondents said that Access is far stronger at handling non-numerical data, like names and descriptions. Non-numerical data plays a significant role in almost any database, and it is important to be able to sort and analyze it. Therefore, database management skills are very essential in business education students entrepreneurial intention.

Microsoft Excel Skills

All the class representatives representing 100% of the participants revealed that Microsoft excel skill is the enabling skill for entrepreneurial intention especially to Office Technology and Management business education students. They said that Microsoft excel skill is essential because it will assist business owners to do all the financial entrance in excel. The class representatives said entrepreneurial intention ensures that the graduate earns money through personal employment. Financial records is also very important in business so that the business owner can keep track of all the income and expenses of the business.

All the class representatives said that Microsoft Excel skills is the most important because everyone goes into business for profit making and the profit and capital of the business must be properly kept in a Microsoft excel record.

Discussion of Findings

The study was on the perceived influence of information and communication technology skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. This discussion was based on the two research questions and two hypotheses presented and statistically analyzed in the study. The findings concerning research question and hypothesis one revealed that lecturers and students of business education in the departments of OTM in North-east Nigeria, agreed that ability to start Microsoft Access, ability to create a database ability to add fields, tables or application parts, ability to create queries, forms, reports and macros, ability to create database using a template, ability to click on file tab, close and display new tab, ability to query the tables and forms created, table import, append, or link to data from another source, ability to add an application part, ability to open an access existing database, ability to type a file name in the box, ability to browse for location to put a database skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The findings also, revealed that there was substantial difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students in federal and state polytechnics regarding the influence of Database Management skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students in the federal and state polytechnics on the extent to which access to database management skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention was rejected.

This corroborates with the study of Nnaji (2014) who concurred that business education is education for and about training in business skills, competencies required for use in business offices, clerical occupations and that which gives occupational identity. This is also confirmed by the study of Njoku (2015) who affirmed that business education is a programme of instruction, which consists of office education, which is a vocational education programme for office career workers through initial refresher and upgrading education. He further explained that general business education is a programme that provides learners with information and

competencies which are needed by all in managing personal business affairs and in using the services of business

The findings concerning research question and hypothesis two revealed that lecturers and students of business education in the departments of OTM in North-east Nigeria, agreed that ability to insert a new worksheets at will, ability to use the time saving shortcut keys, ability to get quick sum of numbers, ability to filter data, ability to paste special feature, ability to insert random numbers, ability to create goal seeking analysis too, ability to insert random fraction numbers and ability to insert serial numbers influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The findings also, revealed that there was substantial difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students in federal and state polytechnics regarding influence of Microsoft excel skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Microsoft excel skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention was rejected. This is in line with the findings of Ekpenyong (2011) who said that among the different forms of education business education which is an aspect of vocational and technical education is of unique nature because it deals with acquisition of skills that prepares individuals for practical and applied skills in different occupation.

Conclusion

Conclusions in this study are made based on the findings from the analysis which revealed the influence of ICT skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention, which are important to lecturers and students especially in this period of high rate of unemployment. ICT skills such as database management skill is very important asset to business education students because they greatly influence their entrepreneurial intention. Business education lecturers must make use of ICT skills in teaching so that business education students will be equipped with ICT skills. Database management and Microsoft excel skills are very essential to OTM students therefore, lecturers should ensure that the students are equipped with these skills, whilst this is done business education students will have the interest to be entrepreneurs after graduation since the required skills have been acquired.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are advanced to channel the way forward:

1. Heads of departments and units should ensure proper supervision of lecturers handling ICT and ICT related courses, so that the right pedagogy is utilized to equip students with knowledge of Database management skills.
2. Microsoft excel skills is necessary to induce business education students entrepreneurial intention therefore, lecturers teaching the course and students who are learners should pay adequate attention in the package so that they can equip themselves with the skills.

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